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AN EXAMINATION OF THE LEGALITY OF COMPULSORY IMMUNIZATION UNDER ISLAMIC LAW AND NIGERIAN LAW

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Abstract

This article, employing doctrinal research methodology, examines the legality of compulsory immunization from Islamic Law and the Nigerian Law. In the process, being the objective of the exercise, the concept of immunization and the scientific process of producing vaccines are discussed. Similarly, the contending views of Islamic law jurists on the validity of Immunization and making the same compulsory have been theorized, contextualized and evaluated. The contentions behind immunization and vaccine rejection are found to be related to the general idea of immunization and the legality of taking substances extracted from products regarded unlawful by Islamic law, such as Pigs. The majority of the Jurists, however, believe that, taking into consideration, the fundamental objectives of Islamic Law on saving lives and preventing harm, immunization, and vaccines are valid, and the same can be made compulsory. Similarly, it has been found that the constitution of Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) has also allowed taking away of the Right to Personal Liberty of the Citizens and accordingly compel them to accept vaccinations. In this regard, the governments in Nigeria, at both the federal and state levels, have legislated and made immunization compulsory. It has been recommended that, governments should engage in a sustainable enlightenment campaign on the validity, importance, and relevance of immunization to the citizens.

Keywords: Legality, Compulsory Immunization, Islamic Law, Nigerian Law

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Immunization is a process by which a person becomes protected against a disease through vaccination.¹ And Vaccination is the act of introducing a vaccine into the body to produce protection from a specific disease.²In this respect, a vaccine is a preparation that is used to stimulate the body's immune response against disease.³ Vaccines are usually administered through needle injections, but some can be administered by mouth or sprayed into the Nose.⁴ The term immunization is often used interchangeably with vaccination or inoculation.⁵ Vaccines are arguably the most important public health tools available today.⁶

The goal of public health is to prevent diseases, and vaccination fulfills that role by protecting people from contracting serious diseases as well as curtailing the spread of such diseases to others.⁷ Immunization is considered as one of the modern medical marvels, an instrument against communicable diseases, saving millions of lives every year from deadly diseases. Since the successful eradication of smallpox with the use of vaccine, many vaccines have become available to man. Of great importance to public and child health are the vaccines against the so-called six killer diseases of childhood: measles, pertussis, diphtheria tetanus, tuberculosis, and poliomyelitis. In the past 2 decades, effective vaccines against the major causes of pneumonia, another childhood killer, have become available. Data from many parts of the world, including African countries have shown the benefits of the pneumococcal and Homophiles influenza types "b" vaccine. The scientific world is still searching for appropriate candidate vaccines for Malaria and H.I.V infections.⁸

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¹ Meaning supplied by the National Center for Immunization and Respiratory Disease, 1, 2021

² Ibid

³ Ibid

⁴ Ibid

⁵ Ibid

⁶Abdulkarim, A.A, R.M Ibrahim, Fawi, A.O, Vaccines and Immunization: The Past, Present and Future in Nigeria, Nigeria Journal of Pediatrics, vo.5 no.7 pg. 1

⁷ Ibid

⁸ Ibid

Immunization is a proven tool for controlling and eliminating life-threatening infectious diseases, in fact, it has been projected that it prevents over 2 million deaths per year. It also avoids suffering disability and death; it is one of the most cost-effective health investments with proven strategies that make it accessible to the most difficult to reach and vulnerable population. It can be delivered effectively through outreach activities. Furthermore, it eases strain on the health care system, and money is saved for use in other health care services. Likewise, it has a clearly defined target group, and finally, it does not require any major change in lifestyle.⁹

(a) Statement of Problem:

Vaccination strongly depends on effective community participation. In other words, people's response is always a factor in the success of immunization or vaccination in a given community. However, despite the apparent usefulness of immunization, many people usually in Africa and Asia are reluctant to participate in immunization exercise. Put differently, some rejects it entirely and many are hesitant in embracing it. Several reasons have been found to be responsible for the hesitancy. In this respect, Immunization rates in Northern Nigeria are some of the lowest in the world.

According to the 2003 National immunization schedule, the percentage of the fully immunized infants in the states to be targeted was less than 1% in Jigawa 1.5% in Yobe, 1.6% in Zamfara and 8.3% in Katsina. As a result, thousands of children are dying as victims of vaccines preventable diseases.¹⁰ In many parts of the North, barely 10 percent of children receive all the routine vaccines. Coverage rates for the vaccine against tetanus among women are equally low.¹¹ There is also a problem of confidence and trust by the public in the healthcare service, resulting from the poor state of the facilities and low standard of delivery. These difficulties have been exacerbated by vertical interventions undertaken by outside agencies, which undermined the capacity of the local service providers to implement sustainable programs. At the family/community level, there is also a low demand for immunization due to a lack of understanding of its value.¹²

⁹Abdulkarim, A.A &ors supra

¹⁰ Ibid

¹¹ Ibid

¹² Ibid

Curiously observed also is the fact that most of the states in the Northern part of Nigeria that are attributed with low patronage of immunization are Muslim dominated states. In fact, this is the trend in many Muslim dominated countries such as Afghanistan, Indonesia, Pakistan, Malaysia and Somalia. The rejection of immunization often resulted in violence, for example, polio immunization workers were at point attacked and killed in Pakistan, Afghanistan, Nigeria, and Somalia.¹³ This vaccine hesitancy is a growing public health concern that has fueled the resurgence of vaccine preventable diseases in several Muslim-Majority countries, including Northern Nigeria, although multiple factors are associated with vaccine hesitancy, certain religious deliberations are significant in determining individual vaccine-related decisions and attitudes. Considering the above highlighted problems, this article seeks to investigate the concept of immunization and the scientific process of producing vaccines, the reasons behind vaccine hesitancy and rejection by people, especially Muslims, the justifiability of the reasons and the extent to which Islamic law approves immunization and whether governments in Nigeria can legislate and make immunization compulsory.

(b) Research Objectives:

The task of undertaking the aforesaid investigation is set to be achieved by pursuing the following objectives: theorizing the concept of immunization and the scientific processes of producing vaccines, identifying and discussing the reasons behind rejection of immunization by Muslims, examining the justifiability of the reasons aforesaid from Islamic law perspective and evaluating the provision of the Islamic law and Nigerian law on compulsory immunization.

(c) Methodology:

This work is carried out by engaging in doctrinal research methodology. In the process, analytical comparative approach is employed by comparing the principles of Islamic law and the provisions of Nigerian laws on the validity of compulsory immunization in Nigeria.

¹³Ebrahim, A. F Vaccination in the Context of Al-Maqasid Al-Shari'ah(Objectives of Divine Law) and Islamic Medical Jurisprudence, An Article of Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (Oman Chapter) Vol. 3 No. 9 April, 2014 Page. 1

Accordingly, the discussion in the paper naturally requires exploration into the postulations and exposition of scholars from other parts of the word on relevant areas.

(d) Research Outline:

This article is divided into three components: the introduction, the main body and the conclusions. The introductory part comprises the background to the study, statement of research problem, research objectives and methodology. The main body contains the discussions and analysis on the subject under consideration. The last part, conclusions, contains the findings and recommendations.

2.0 MAIN BODY

2.1 IMMUNIZATION AND THE SCIENTIFIC PROCESSES OF PRODUCING VACCINES

Immunization is a process by which a person becomes protected against a disease through vaccination. It is an aspect of public health that is hinged on preventing disease. It has been submitted that it is much easier and more cost-effective to prevent a disease than to treat it.¹⁴ The aim of immunization is to protect people from serious diseases and also prevent the spread of those diseases to others.¹⁵ Over the years, immunizations have thwarted epidemics of once infectious diseases such as measles; mumps, and whooping cough. Furthermore, because of immunization, we have seen the near eradication of others such as polio and smallpox.¹⁶ Immunization is generally being done by vaccination. Vaccination is the act of introducing a vaccine into the body to produce protection from a specific disease.¹⁷ It is basically being done by safely and effectively using a small amount of a weakened or killed virus or bacteria or bits of lab-made protein that imitate the virus to prevent infection. When a body is immunized by being injected with the substance aforementioned, its immune system is triggered, causing it to either produce antibodies to that particular ailment or induce other process that enhance immunity. Therefore, if the body is ever exposed to the actual disease-causing organism, the immune system is

¹⁴ Goodman, S. Immunization and Vaccination, available at Mw. WebMD, LLC, 2020 Accessed on the 30th of May, 2023 around 6:00pm Pg. 1

¹⁵ Ibid

¹⁶ Ibid

¹⁷ Ibid

prepared to fight the infection. A vaccine will usually prevent the onset of a disease or else reduce its severity.¹⁸

Vaccination is made to combat a spreading infectious disease such as Hepatitis 'B', Rotavirus, Measles, Covid-19, and Hepatitis 'A' or being administered to children with a view to strengthening their immune system against certain diseases that are highly harmful, and their weak immune system may not be able to deal with.¹⁹

2.2 THE SCIENTIFIC PROCESS OF PRODUCING VACCINE

Vaccination is the administration of antigenic materials to produce immunity to a disease. It was originally used specifically to describe the injection of small Pox.²⁰ The creation of vaccine involves scientists and medical experts from around the world.²¹ It typically requires 10-15 years of research before a vaccine is made available to the public.²² The first step of this extensive process involved several years of laboratory research, in which scientists and researchers identified an Antigen that can prevent a disease.²³

As vaccines are generally complex biological products, numerous animals' derived products are often used in their manufacture. These products are essential to ensure the safety, potency, and stability of the product and their use is highly regulated. Vaccines are life-saving medicinal products which are given to protect individuals against serious infections. Some vaccines contain a small number of viruses or bacteria that have been inactivated by chemical treatment. These "killed" vaccines cannot cause the disease they prevent. Other vaccines contain microorganisms which, although alive, cannot cause serious disease (live attenuated) vaccines. Vaccines may also be composed of purified fractions of these microorganisms or even from selected components that are synthesized using DNA technology.²⁴ Newer vaccines are also being used where genetic

¹⁸ Ibid

¹⁹ Ibid

²⁰ Abdulkarim, A.A & O K Vaccines and Immunization the Past, Present and Future in Nigeria: Supra. P.I

²¹ Offitt, P. The Science Behind Vaccine Research and Testing contained in a Video Reviewed by Paul, A, on August, 18, 2021

²² Ibid

²³ Ibid

²⁴ Ibid

material is delivered into the host cells and the body's own cells then generate a protein from the target organism.²⁵

Bacterial cultures and viral cell lines need to be grown in a special liquid called culture media, as do the bacterial, insect or mammalian cells that are used to express recombinant proteins. Vaccines are usually made by growing cultures of the target virus or bacterium. Virus need to grow in cells, and so vaccine viruses are often grown in eggs (e.g., influenza) or in cell lines derived from mammals, including humans. These cell lines used to grow the virus will derive from a primary culture of cell from organs of a single animal which has been propagated repeatedly in the laboratory, typically over many decades, for example, measles vaccine is grown in chick embryo cells lines and polio vaccines are grown in a mouse cell line. Another animal cell now being used to make egg free flu vaccine was derived in 1958 from the kidney of a cocker spaniel. Using these cells line avoids any ongoing harm to animals. The best-known human cell line is MRC 5; these cells derive from the lung of a 14weeks old male fetus from a pregnancy that was terminated for medical reasons in 1966. This cell line is used to grow virus for vaccines against rubella, chicken pox and hepatitis 'A'. Other fetal cell lines, collected in the 1970s and 1980s have been used for other vaccines including influenza and some new (Covid-19) vaccines. No fetal material is present in the final vaccine.²⁶

The moral issues around the use of vaccines grown on fetal cell lines have been discussed within the Catholic Church. The Church notes that the cell lines are distant from the initial termination, and states that acceptance of such vaccines where there is no appropriate alternative does not signify co-operation with abortion.²⁷

Animal enzymes are also used during the manufacture of vaccine viruses, but subsequent washing, purification and dilution steps remove them from the final vaccines. One example is Trypsin, normally derived from pigs which is widely used during the manufacture of vaccines, usually being added to the final cell culture to activate the vaccine virus.²⁸

²⁵ Ibid

²⁶ Offitt, P.A, "The Science Behind Vaccine Research and Testing" contained in a Video Reviewed by Paul, A, on August, 18, 2021

²⁷ Ibid

²⁸ Ibid

Trypsin is also used during the manufacture of other medical products, such as insulin and heparin. Although the enzyme is used as a raw-material, in the early steps of the vaccine manufacturing, it is being eliminated in the later steps of the manufacturing process.²⁹

Porcine Trypsin is also used in some injected influenza vaccines, and in vaccines against Rota virus, chicken pox and polio. Its use and subsequent eliminated from the vaccines have acceptable by some Muslim Scholars.³⁰ Furthermore, highly processed derivatives of animal materials are occasionally used in the finished vaccine product. These derivatives are called excipients, and perform an important function in ensuring the vaccine is safe and effective.³¹

Some chemicals, called adjuvants, are used to improve the immune response to vaccines. One example of an adjuvant that is derived from animals is squalene oil that is being extracted from shark's liver. This adjuvant is used in the influenza vaccine that is given to the elderly where it improves the level of protection in an age group where responses to vaccines are normally reduced. A similar adjuvant is being used in one of the new Covid-19 vaccines³².

2.2 WHAT ARE THE REASONS BEHIND VACCINE REJECTION AND HESITANCY AMONG MUSLIMS AND OTHERS?

Vaccine hesitancy is a growing public health concern that has fueled the resurgence of vaccine-preventable diseases in several Muslim majority countries. As pointed out earlier, although multiple factors are associated with vaccine hesitancy, certain religious deliberations are significant in determining individual vaccine related decisions and attitudes.³³ It has been observed that, the leading factors contributing to vaccines hesitancy include socio-cultural differences, unfamiliarity with vaccine preventable

²⁹Ibid

³⁰ Ibid

³¹ Ibid

³²Offitt, P. The Science Behind Vaccine Research and Testing contained in a Video Reviewed by Paul, A, on August, 18, 2021

³³ Al Suwaidi, R., Hammad, A.A, El Barazi, I Hussain, M.S Vaccine Hesitancy within the Muslim Community: Islamic Faith and Public Health Perspectives, Journal of Human Vaccines & Immuno Therapeutics, Published online, 2023, March 13 pg.27

diseases, lack of understanding of the coincidence and insignificant adverse effects of vaccines, lack of trust in public health messages and media misinformation.³⁴

Remarkably, religious beliefs have been cited as major drivers of vaccine hesitancy and refusal. Religious factors are distinct from other factors. This is because they are generally linked to core beliefs, which makes it extremely difficult to convince individuals to change their views on immunization, and are mostly linked to a complete refusal of vaccines rather than vaccine hesitancy.³⁵ Although most religions, including Christianity, Islam, Hinduism, and Judaism do not oppose the idea of vaccination, certain religious considerations or related socio-cultural reasons play significant roles in shaping vaccine attitudes, beliefs, and decisions. The most apparent religious consideration that oppose immunization are linked to violation of prohibitions against taking life, violation of dietary laws (e.g. Non-Halal-based vaccine) or interference with the natural order by not letting events take their course.³⁶

Northern Nigeria is a Muslim majority region, and like most Muslim majority countries of Africa and Asia, the people are mostly reluctant to accept and participate in immunization activities because of the following documented and verifiable reasons:

- a) There is a faith-based concern about the general concept of immunization.

It could be recalled that immunization is predicated on prevention of contracting with a disease or its spread. In other words, the idea of immunization is pillowed on prevention rather than cure. Some Muslim Scholars are of the view that Allah *SubhanahuWataala* has created human being with the utmost immune system and vaccines were unnecessary.³⁷ This is what *Al-Suwaidi* called religious health fatalism. He explained the term as a belief that health outcomes are inevitable and are pre-determined by God.³⁸ However, on this, many Islamic scholars and researchers maintain that the Holy Prophet had set the issue of taking medicine and seeking treatment in its proper sense when he was asked whether taking medicine contradicts or reverses the destiny and fate of Almighty Allah, he

³⁴ Ibid

³⁵ Ibid

³⁶ Ibid

³⁷ Al-Suwaidi supra

³⁸ Ibid P. 24-25

responded that seeking treatment is actually from God's fate and destiny. Based on this, Islamic scholars consider vaccination a religious obligation. In 1992, the International Islamic Fiqh academy issued a statement indicating that among the objectives of Sharia is the preservation of life. Accordingly, when not seeking medical treatment may lead to infection or death to others, then seeking medical treatment may be considered a religious obligation. Similarly, in 2016, the Fatwa committee of Perlis in Malaysia issued a statement indicating that vaccination is an Islamic obligation³⁹.

Closely related to this, some people believe that it is not valid to engage in preventing the occurrence of a disease that has not yet come but many Islamic jurists opine that there is nothing wrong in doing that if one fears that a disease could occur because of an imminent out-break of an epidemic or other factors that could cause the onset of the disease. On this, Shaykh Abdul Aziz bin Baz, who was a Grand Mufti of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia from 1999, was asked about the permissibility of resorting to being vaccinated before the onset of the disease. He answered that it was valid and justified the same by quoting an authentic Hadith (saying or action) of the holy Prophet Muhammad as follows: "whoever eats seven Medinan dates in the morning will not be harmed by witchcraft or poison". In other words, by eating those dates, one would be warding off a problem before it occurs. Likewise, seeking to be vaccinated from certain diseases would be a form of protection from the diseases.⁴⁰

Another contention is the fact that immunization generally involves tampering with human immune system to make it prepared for an incoming disease. This aspect of it is also contested by some Muslims to the effect that immunization is an alteration of the creation of the Almighty Allah, and same is not in consonance with the position of Islamic Injunction that prohibits such alteration. On this, it has been submitted that *Al-Biruni, Ibn Hazam, Ibn Taymiyyah* and *Ibn Al-Qayyum* have emphasized that the prohibition of such alteration is based on the natural philosophy of law ordained by Allah, based on the Qur'anic Verse 30:30 where the Almighty Allah stated: "the constitution of Allah according to which he hath

³⁹ Ibid

⁴⁰ Ibrahim, A.F.M. Vaccination in the Context of Al- Maqasid –al- Sharia (Objectives of Divine Law) and Islamic Medical Jurisprudence, *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (Oman Chapter)* Vol.3 No.9 April 2014 pg.49

constituted mankind, no altering therein Allah's creation. However, a counterargument on this may be put forth as follows: The maxim, necessity permits prohibitions means that when one is in a situation that endangers one's life, the one whose life is threatened could do what is, in normal circumstances, prohibited to save his life. For instance, when one is starved, and there is no halal food or water in sight, one could consume what is, under normal circumstances, prohibited to save his life⁴¹. This is what is termed as the doctrine of necessity.

(b) Many Islamic Scholars and intellectuals are not comfortable with the general procedure of producing vaccines, particularly the substances being used in producing and preserving them. In this regard, the use of substance obtained from pigs to develop vaccines is one of the most contentious aspects of vaccine acceptance or otherwise by Muslim population in the whole world, including those of Northern Nigeria. For example, in Indonesia, a country with the largest Muslim Population, a study was conducted in that respect. The result explored the views of religious and community leaders regarding the rotavirus vaccine where vaccine acceptance is complicated because of the use of porcine Trypsin during the manufacturing process. This raised concern about the rotavirus vaccine being non-permissible. Although participating religious leaders recognized that rotavirus diarrhea can be severe, and vaccination is advisable, they believed that a *Halal* label was required for community acceptance and maintenance of trust.⁴²

In 2018, a fatwa, (a formal ruling by religious authority) issued by Indonesian Islamic clerics declared measles and rubella vaccine forbidden under sharia because pig components were used to manufacture it. Consequently, immunization rates have significantly dropped, reaching as low as 8% in Aceh, a province being ruled by sharia.⁴³

In Pakistan, a country with the second-largest Muslim population worldwide, has the third-highest burden of child mortality, and ranks third globally for the most under vaccinated children. In a study exploring reasons for non-vaccination in pediatric patients visiting tertiary care centers, the most common reasons for the non-vaccination were the

⁴¹ Engku, M.T.E,op.cit P.610

⁴² Al Suwaidi op.cit

⁴³ Ibid

lack of knowledge and religious taboos. The authority of this study stated that they encountered disagreement against vaccination among most religious leaders in the country, with statements such as: “the Imam (religious leader) has forbidden the use of vaccines as they contain porcine components”. It is to be noted that it is not only Muslims that reject vaccines because of pig or other animal components used to develop same. Jews also doesn’t consume pig and its products, including vaccine. In 2013, in relation to porcine gelatin in the nasal flu vaccine, the UK Health security agency had consulted the Jewish Kashrut and Medicines Information Service, who noted that porcine and other animal derived ingredients are acceptable in non-oral products including vaccine even those administered via the nose.⁴⁴

Similarly, in India, Hindus have questioned the inclusion of cow blood in the Covid-19 vaccine developed by Pfizer, Moderna, Astrazeneca and Bharat Biotech’s Coraxin.⁴⁵ Accordingly, Swami Chakrapani, the President of the Hindu Mahasabha, had written to President Ram Nath Kovind demanding that the government and pharmaceutical companies clarify whether the Covid-19 vaccine contains cow’s blood or not.⁴⁶

(c) Other skepticisms towards vaccines:

Apart from issues related to the substance being used to develop vaccines, there are concern that, immunization and campaigns for vaccination are conspiracies by pharmaceutical companies to sell their medicine.⁴⁷ Some Muslims maintain that vaccinations are part of the western conspiracy to eradicate Muslims. In Pakistan for example, an Imam was quoted saying that vaccination is a conspiracy of the Zionists, vaccinating our children will inevitably make them sterile.⁴⁸

(d) The side effects of immunization:

One such concern stems from an article by Andrew Wakefield that MMR or other vaccines containing certain preservative additives cause irreversible harm such as autism. Investigations into the matter have found an unethical research practice where Wakefield

⁴⁴ Mirza A, Coronavirus Vaccine: is it Halal or not? Available at asadmira@Mcognition, P.1

⁴⁵ Ibid p.4

⁴⁶ Al-Suwaidi, supra. P. 24

⁴⁷ Ibid

⁴⁸ Ibid

received funds from those who were in a legal battle with vaccine manufactures. Several scientific investigations conducted to find the truth about Wakefield's claims showed that there was no relation between vaccinations and autism whatsoever.⁴⁹

It has been further observed that, frightening information about the social networks written by those who claim to be highly qualified or Doctors in one of the reasons parents are reluctant to have their children vaccinated. Accordingly, the Ministry of Health in Malaysia records that, the number of cases of parents rejecting vaccinations had increased from 470 cases in 2013 to 1292 in 2014, in the first three months of 2016, there were 500 cases of rejection by parents.⁵⁰ However, this fear could somehow be justified if the experience of people of Kano State of Nigeria with Pfizer pharmaceutical company is considered.

In 1996, during the worst ever meningitis epidemics, a hundred children were given an experimental oral antibiotic called Trovan, while a further hundred received ceftriaxone, the gold standard treatment of modern medicine. Five children died in Trovan and six on ceftriaxone, the gold standard treatment of modern medicine. Five children died on Trovan and six on ceftriaxone. But later it was claimed that Pfizer did not have proper consent from parents to use an experimental drug on their children, and questions were raised over the documentation of the trial. Legal action filed against the company alleged that some received a dose lower than recommended, leaving many children with brain damage, paralysis or slurred speech. The U.S. base Pfizer argued that meningitis and not its antibiotics that led to the death of 11 children and harm to dozens of others. But in 2009 it reached a tentative out of court settlement with the Kano State Government worth \$ 75m.⁵¹ The Families of four of the children each collected cheque for \$ 175,000 from a Compensation Trust Fund after submitting a DNA samples to show that the dead children were their off springs.⁵²

⁴⁹ Amin, N.S.B, Shafy, A.A The Legality of Immunization in Islamic Law Journal of Asian and African Social Science and Humanities, vol. 1 2023 pg. 39-40

⁵⁰Ali. E.M.T Mohd Z, Al-Shafi'i O. M M Vaccinations From the Perspectives of Islamic Legal Maxim, International Journal of Academic Research in Business & Social Sciences, 2017 V.4 p 12

⁵¹ Pfizer Pays out to Nigerian Families of Meningitis Drug Trial Victims. Reported by the Guardian on the 12th of August, 2011 Pg. 1

⁵² Ibid

2.3. THE LEGALITY OF IMMUNIZATION/ VACCINATION FROM THE PERSPECTIVES OF ISLAMIC LAW

Contemporary Islamic Scholars have expressed contending views about the legality of immunization as follows:

There are scholars who believe that immunization and vaccination in particulars are illegal and contrary to the provision of Islamic law. The bases of their arguments are mostly on the concept and procedure of immunization i.e. altering the Human Immune system and the substance being used in developing vaccines. These points have been discussed above.

On the other hand, there are scholars who expressed opinions supporting immunization. In the process, they cited several Islamic law authorities and accordingly neutralizes the positions of those are against it.

Ebrahim, A, F.M Muhammad Karyani Yan Mardian, Noor Shuwadati, Ahmed AffanShafy, Engku Muhammad Tajuddin, Muhammad MuneerOlodo, Al-Shafi', Asad Mirza Ahmed, Al-Suwaidi, Hamza Abed al Karim, Iffatel-Barazi, and Muhammad SheikHussaini believe that: Firstly, concerning the validity of vaccination in the light of alteration of human immune system and seeking preventive medicine, the jurists opined that: the alteration is valid, since its purpose is to trigger the immune system, to respond to an infection. Accordingly, Noor, Shuhadawati Binti Muhammad Amin and Ahmed Amin opined that modern vaccines in all of their different forms functions to trigger an immune response by the immune system and to create memory cell, which will remain in the body and instruct B-L Lymphocytes to produce specific antibodies to address a specific pathogen or disease causing agent. On this, they opined that it is the intention of the alteration that should be considered. Therefore, the right guidance should be found in the Islamic law maxim of: Actions or a matter is determined according to the intention. This maxim is derived from the prophetic tradition that says: "the deeds, depends upon the intention" Imam al Shafi'i had highlighted the importance of this maxim and related that it is third in Islamic Jurisprudence.⁵³ In other words, it is the purpose of the alteration that should be

⁵³ Noor, S.M.A, Shafy, A.A The Legality of Immunization in Islamic Law, Journal of Asia and Africa Social Science and Humanities, Vol. 8, No.1 2027 Pg 33-34-5

considered.⁵⁴ Therefore, it could be inferred from this maxim that, even if immunization entails the alteration of the Human immune system, the intention of the alteration is what should be considered in determining its validity or otherwise. Regarding an agreement about seeking preventive medicines, it has been submitted that, Islamic law and its objectives maintain that harm, injury, and loss should be avoided, and therefore, the primary objective of Islamic law is sustaining life. Islamic law dictates prevention of harm and anything that may harm people. There were also several instances where the holy prophet decreed that if there is a breakout of contagious illnesses such as plague, people are advised to halt their movement until the outbreak is controlled.⁵⁵ Similarly, the Holy prophet had instructed Muslims to isolate the sick as a precaution from an outbreak.⁵⁶ Secondly, pertaining to the substances being used in developing vaccines, the jurists are of the view that, when it comes to passing verdict on any medical treatment, Muslim Jurists should examine the treatment procedure as well as the substances being used for the treatment to determine the legality of the treatment or medication. Therefore, when it comes to content of vaccination, mostly the doubts are regarding substances which are prohibited such as intoxicants, non-halal animal products and products sourced in contradiction to Islamic law. One such ingredient is porcine gelatin. Islamic legal scholars have declared, that based on Islamic law, denatured porcine gelatin does not fit into the prohibited porcine product category, since its very nature has been altered to the stage that it cannot be considered as a general porcine product.

Just for the sake of agreement, if such a product in trace amounts are considered prohibited, if it is deemed necessary to preserve life, then according to the legal maxim: Necessity renders prohibited thing permissible, taking such substances is allowed.

Thus, it is based on these maxims; the then Grand Mufti of Saudi Arabia issued a legal opinion stating the legality and permissibility of the polio vaccine.⁵⁷

⁵⁴Ibid

⁵⁵ Noor, S.M.A. Shafy, A. "The Legality of Immunization in Islamic Law", Journal of Asia and Africa Social Sciences and Humanities, Vol. 8, No.1 2027 Pg 33-34-5

⁵⁶ Ibid

⁵⁷Ibid

A similar legal opinion regarding Trypsin was issued in 2003 by the European council of fatwa and research headed by then the President of the council, Sheikh Yusuf Al-Qardawi stating that even though Trypsin is an enzyme derived from pork pancreas, and its general status is prohibition, it is permissible to use same since an alternative was not available and that the repercussions are greater harm.⁵⁸

Similarly, a leading Islamic school, Akhtatulwasiy, former Professor of Islamic studies at Jami'a Millia Islamia, trying to put at rest the whole issue, opines that for Muslims pork and Alcohol are not permissible for eating and drinking purposes, but if a part of these is used for medicinal purpose, then it is allowed in Islam, as that medicine will be taken for the express purpose of saving a life, which is allowed in Islam. Furthermore, he asserted that, according to Islamic Jurists, a person suffering from hunger for more than three days and nearer to death is also allowed to eat the meat of a dead animal to survive.⁵⁹

Moreover, researchers see the possibility of employing the *Istihala* rule in Islamic Jurisprudence. It refers to the transformation of a substance into another different from it by name, characteristic and quality.⁶⁰ Therefore, Forbidden substances if transformed very well may be permissible. Therefore, based on the majority rulings, it can be inferred that it is permissible to take the vaccines.⁶¹ The contention now is, can governments in Nigeria make law to make immunization/vaccination compulsory?

(i) Islamic Law Perspective on Making Immunization Compulsory:

Considering the disposition and exposition of the Islamic jurists to the effect that immunization is valid; they even go further to make it obligatory upon authorities to make the same compulsory to the concern subjects. On this, it has been submitted that, the objective of a vaccine mandate is to ensure that a communicable disease does not spread within the community, and vulnerable individuals are protected by herd immunity.⁶²

Thus, a state might make it obligatory upon all the citizens and residence to vaccinate. To this end, since in Islamic law it is an obligation upon the state to ensure the safety of the

⁵⁸ Ibid

⁵⁹ Mirza, A. Coronavirus Vaccine is it Halal or not? Supra P.5

⁶⁰ Al-Suwaidi, op. cit.

⁶¹ Ibid

⁶² Noor, SBMA, Shafyop.cit

people, then laws can be enacted in line with the objectives of Islamic law in accordance with the legal maxim: The action of a leader (State) shall be driven by the interest of the people. Similarly, the state may infringe on individual liberties or freedoms to ensure the safety and security of the communities, since the rights of a community take precedence over individual rights in general.⁶³In this regard, the Islamic law Maxim states: “The ruler’s decision is dictated in favour of his people”. It means that, every decision made by the ruler must be based on the beneficial aspect or priorities (*Maslaha*). The beneficial aspects here mean benefits to the public.⁶⁴On the other hand, Muslims are obligated to be respectful and obedient to the instructions of their authorities, especially with regard to issues related to the public interest, particularly the protection of life.⁶⁵

2.4 COMPULSORY VACCINATION FROM THE PERSPECTIVES OF NIGERIAN LAWS

Nigeria is one of the 10 countries in the world where most of the incompletely immunized children live, despite the giant investments in immunization program by governmental and non-governmental organizations.⁶⁶ As pointed earlier, one of the underlying factors towards this situation is the reluctance of the people to accept the immunization. Now, considering its obvious benefits as highlighted above, can the government of Nigeria compel the citizens to submit themselves or their children to be immunized against a disease? The answer to this question can be best answered if the provisions of the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 on the relevant citizen’s rights and related matters are briefly emboldened and discussed. Generally speaking, the constitution prohibits compelling people or the citizens to do something for which their minds are against for. Therefore, in this respect, subjecting an unwilling citizen or any person to compulsory immunization is mostly not allowed. Accordingly, Section 35 of the Constitution provides that every person shall be entitled to his personal liberty. However, section 35(1) (e) provides an exception to the effect that notwithstanding the aforesaid prohibition, the right aforesaid can be taken away in the case of persons suffering from an

⁶³ Ali, E.M.T.E, Muhammed, Z.M, Al-Shafi’i M.O Vaccination from the Perspectives of Islamic Legal Maxim International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences, 2017, vol. No. 12 p.g 611

⁶⁴Ibid

⁶⁵ Ibid

⁶⁶Adedokun, et al Incomplete Childhood Immunization in Nigeria: aMulti-Level Analysis of Individual and Contextual Factors a Research Article of the BMC Public Health (2017) 17:236 Pg.1

infectious or contagious disease. Therefore, it can be inferred, a person suffering from infectious disease may be compelled to be immunized. By extension, on analogy, even those that are vulnerable to a disease can thus be compelled. It is also a settled constitutional principle premised on section 45 of the constitution that the fundamental rights contained in sections 37⁶⁷, 38⁶⁸, 39⁶⁹, 40⁷⁰ and 41⁷¹ can be taken away in the interest of defense, public morality or public health. Therefore, one may be right to say that the rights given in the sections are not absolute. Vaccination, about infectious or contagious disease, is a medium through which a community can be protected to prevent a spiral of the disease(s), as such, the argument can be made the Right to Personal Liberty, including the right to determine whether to be vaccinated, can be derogated from to protect a community from an infectious or contagious disease insofar as the derogation is in line with a procedure permitted by law.⁷²

In accordance with the above highlighted constitutional provisions, the Nigerian Federal legislature made sure that a provision was made for compulsory immunization to children in Nigeria in the Child Rights Act of 2003. The law provides that every parent, guardian, or people having the care and custody of a child under the age of two years shall ensure that the child is provided with full immunization.⁷³ Similarly, the government of Jigawa state at a point had enacted a Law⁷⁴ for compulsory immunization of persons against yellow fever and other infectious diseases. The law is a short legislation with only 12 sections that pertains to liability to be inoculated, inoculation of adults, inoculation of children and penalty among other things.

The law provides that the Governor of the state may, by an order, direct that all persons or any specified class or classes of persons being or coming within such area in the state as may be prescribed in the order, shall be liable to be inoculated against yellow

⁶⁷ Right to Private and Family Life

⁶⁸ Right to Freedom of Thought, Conscience and Religion

⁶⁹ Right to Freedom of Expression

⁷⁰ Right to Peaceful Assembly and Association

⁷¹ Right to Freedom of Movement

⁷² Mardian, Y. et al Sharia Islamic Law Perspectives of Covid 19 Vaccines an article of the Journal of Disease Prevention and Control Policy, Volume 2 2021 pg 55

⁷³ Section 13(4) of the Child Rights Act 2003

⁷⁴ Yellow Fever and Infectious Diseases (Immunization) Law CAP.Y1, vol.4 Laws of Jigawa State, 2012

fever.⁷⁵ Accordingly, every adult to whom an order aforesaid is made, shall within seven days of the coming into force of such order or within seven days of the coming into force of such order, or within seven days of entering into a prescribed area, save on temporary basis, presents himself to a health officer for examination and, if necessary, inoculation against yellow fever, and shall subsequently attend at such time and at such place as the health officer may direct for the purposes of such examination and inoculation.⁷⁶ Regarding children, however, the law provides that the parent of a child to whom an order is made shall, if such child is of the age of eighteen months or over at the date on which the order comes into force or on which such child enters into a prescribed area, save on a temporary visit, within seven days of the happening of either event bring such child to a health officer for examination, and if necessary, inoculated against yellow fever and shall subsequently bring such child to such place and at such time as the health officer may direct for the purposes of such examination and inoculation.⁷⁷ The Law provides for a penalty against any person who without reasonable cause fails to comply with the law or of any rule made thereunder shall be liable on conviction for a first offense to a fine of Five Thousand Naira or to imprisonment for six months or to both such fine and imprisonment and on conviction for a second or subsequent offense to a fine of five thousand Naira or to an imprisonment for one year or to both such fine and imprisonment.⁷⁸

3.0 CONCLUSIONS

SUMMARY

By way of Doctrinal Research Methodology, this article discussed the scientific concept of immunization and the components being used in producing vaccines. In the process, immunization is a preventive mechanism against the contraction or spread of a disease and it is being done by triggering the human immune system to prepare for an incoming infection. The substance used in such triggering are called vaccines. These substances are extracted from animals, microorganisms and plants. It has been understood that immunization is somehow rejected by Muslims and the reasons are related to the concept

⁷⁵ Section 3, Yellow Fever and Infectious Diseases (Immunization) Law Cap Y1, Laws of Jigawa State 2012

⁷⁶ Section 4 ibid

⁷⁷ Section 5 ibid

⁷⁸ Section 10 Yellow Fever and Infectious Diseases (Immunization) Law CAP Y1, Laws of Jigawa State 2012

of immunization and the fact that some of the substances are extracted from animals that are not permissible for Muslims consumptions such as pigs. However, Islamic Jurists have expressed divergent opinions about the validity of immunization and use of substances considered primarily unlawful for Muslims consumption. The Majority opinion is to the effect that taking into consideration the intention and purpose of the activity at one hand and the various objectives of Islamic Law, Immunization is valid and could be made compulsory for Muslims. From conventional law perspectives, however, it could be said that, the Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria has approved the taking away of the Right to Personal Liberty of the Citizens and accordingly compel them to be vaccinated, and in the process both the state and federal legislatures have enacted laws for the purpose.

FINDINGS

It has been found that notwithstanding several reservations about the validity of immunization, and vaccines, from Islamic Law perspective, immunization and vaccines are valid, lawful, and permissible. Furthermore, it has been found that the reasons behind the vaccine hesitancy particularly among the Muslims are the fact that the concept of immunization and the procedure for making the vaccines are mostly not in accordance with the principles of Islamic law. Most notably among the reasons is the use of substances extracted from animals, the consumption of which is generally not acceptable under Islamic law. There are also contentions about prevention of disease before its occurrence and the problem related to the fact that immunization entails the alteration of human immune system that is not also generally acceptable. In addition, it has also been found that the reasons are not justifiable because the contentions are resolved by contemporary Islamic jurists who used various Islamic law principles derived from the primary and secondary sources of the law, and successfully neutralize the objections highlighted above. In essence, using the authorities cited, and notably based on the various principles of fundamental objectives of Islamic law, immunization is valid and the reasons behind vaccine hesitancy are not justifiable. Moreover, it has been found that Islamic law has approved immunization without any limitation in so far as lives and well-being of the people is being threatened; this is based on the objective of Islamic law that has the protection of life as one of its top priorities. In the same vein, it has been found that both

Islamic law and Nigerian Law have generally accepted that, due to the importance of immunization, governments can legislate to make same compulsory and accordingly, the governments in Nigeria, both at the federal and states level have enacted laws to make immunizations compulsory.

OBSERVATION

It has been observed that most of the issues surrounding immunization and vaccines are related to misinformation, ignorance, and lack of awareness for the people and lack of diligence on the part of the government to educate people about the merits of immunization and the validity of taking vaccinations from both the perspectives of Islamic Law and the Nigerian Law.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It has been recommended that, even though this work has found out that immunization is valid and governments can legislate and have off course legislate, to make same compulsory to the citizens, there is need for governments to engage in a wide societal re-orientation and sustainable enlightenment exercise to get the acceptance of people to be immunized.